

Bullying among Secondary Level Students in Selected Schools of Pokhara, Nepal

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ABSTRACT

Background: Bullying is a multidimensional form of abuse that is most witnessed in schools. It is any pattern of negative behavior or aggressiveness intended to injure or annoy someone. This study aims to identify the status of different types of bullying experienced by secondary-level school students.

Methodology: A cross-sectional study was conducted among 137 secondary level students. Proportionate stratified sampling technique was used to find out the number of samples from each class and a lottery method without replacement was used to select the samples from each class. A Semi-structured self-administered questionnaire was used to collect the data. Data was analyzed by using descriptive statistics as well as inferential statistics. Research ethics was maintained throughout the study.

Result: The findings of the study revealed that nearly 75 percent of the respondents were bullied at school and some of them (10.94 percent) were bullied even at home. Among the bullied students, 60.39 percent were boys. Nearly 45 percent had experienced low bullying, 41.59 percent had average bullying and nearly 14 percent had high bullying. There was a statistically significant association between the status of bullying and the sex of respondents ($p=0.04$), fathers' occupation ($p=0.04$), and mothers' occupation ($p=0.01$).

Conclusion: Majority of the respondents were victims of bullying at school. The most common form of bullying among students was verbal followed by physical and sexual. Schools can organize an awareness-raising program on bullying for school children to prevent emerging mental health issues.

Keywords: Bullying, Secondary level students, School

INTRODUCTION

Bullying is any needless offensive behavior by a different group of people who are with the victim(s) and are recurrent. It can affect physical, psychological, social, or academic performance of students.^[1,2]

Bullying is a multidimensional form of abuse that is most commonly witnessed in schools. Teasing, name-calling, mockery, threats, harassment, taunting, hazing, social exclusion, or rumors have been identified as being prevalent internationally.^[3] The act of harassing another person often involves aggression, ridicule, or even humiliation of the victim.^[4] Globally, the prevalence of bullying was 60%.^[5] Body appearance is one of the top two most common types of bullying across all regions, the second most frequent grounds for bullying reported by kids are race, nationality, or color.^[6] According to Global School-Based Student Health Survey, Nepal recorded the highest prevalence of bullying victims in Southeast Asia (51%), which includes being physically, emotionally, and sexually harassed, while 14.4% of students experience cyber bullying and 45% engage in bullying themselves. Bullying mostly happened in classrooms^[7,8]. Globally, 14% of bullied students struggle academically.^[5] The bullying epidemic in the US causes more than 160,000 children to stay home from school every day.^[9] Aggressive children and teenagers are masters at influencing or manipulating others. Additionally, many had experienced physical bullying themselves and at least 10% experience it frequently.^[10]

Bullying is one of the most prevalent problems of Nepal; every school is affected by bullying, which is why some student's academic performance has not improved. It can lead to poor academic performance and even dropping out of school. So that this study aims to identify the status of different types of bullying experienced by secondary-level school students.

METHODOLOGY

A cross-sectional study was conducted to assess the status of bullying among 137 students studying in grade 9,10,11 and 12 in Shishu Niketan Higher Secondary School of Pokhara Metropolitan City-17, Kaski, Nepal. The total students from these classes were 315. Students above 18 years and below 13 years were excluded from the study. Probability proportionate stratified sampling technique was used to find out the number of samples from each class and finally a lottery method without replacement was used to select the samples. Data was collected by the researcher from August 14 to August 21 by using a semi-structured self-administered questionnaire.

The content validity of the instrument was maintained by extensive literature review and incorporating the opinions of the subject experts, and research advisors. Pretesting of the instrument was done among 10% of the sample size and minor modifications on tool were made as well. Reliability of the instrument was calculated by using Karl Pearson's correlation coefficient test. The score was 0.815 which indicates the instrument was reliable.

Data was collected after getting approval from Institutional Review Committee (IRC), at Pokhara University. Written permission was obtained from the school authority. As the respondents were under 18 years, assent consent was obtained from the parents of each student on the day before data collection. Anonymity was maintained throughout the study. Queries of the respondents were clarified after data collection. The collected data were coded and entered in to Epi Data 3.1 version and exported to SPSS version 23 for further analysis. Descriptive data was analyzed by using mean, frequency, and

percentage. The chi-square test was used to find the association between dependent and independent variables. The level of significance was considered at 5% with p-value <0.05 and 95% confidence interval.

RESULTS

Table 1: Socio-Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

n=137

Variables	Frequency(f)	Percentage (%)
Age in completed years		
≤15	95	69.35
>15	42	30.65
Mean age ± SD = 15.06 ± 1.08		
Sex		
Male	77	56.21
Female	60	43.79
Ethnicity		
Brahmin/ Chhetri	101	73.72
Janajati	36	26.28
Religion		
Hinduism	118	86.20
Buddhism	16	11.80
Christian	2	1.45
Muslim	1	0.55
Grade/Class		
Class 9	60	43.79
Class 10	49	35.76
Class 11	18	13.13
Class 12	10	7.32
Academic Performance		
Outstanding	20	14.59
Excellent	32	23.35
Very Good	37	27.00
Good	40	29.19
Satisfactory	8	5.87
Father's Education Status		
Illiterate	2	1.45
Basic Level (1-8)	4	2.91
Secondary Level (9-12)	55	40.14

Bachelor's Degree & Above	76	55.50
Mother's Education Status		
Illiterate	2	1.45
Basic Level (1-8)	16	11.67
Secondary Level (9-12)	54	39.41
Bachelor's Degree & Above	67	48.90
Occupation of Father		
Business	71	51.82
Service	38	27.73
Foreign Employed	28	20.4
Occupation of Mother		
Housemaker	64	46.71
Service	38	27.73
Business	35	25.54

(Table 1) depicts that the mean age of the respondents was found to be 15.06 (SD=1.08). Majority were belongs to age group 13-15years. More than 50 percent were male, 86.13 percent followed Hinduism. Nearly 74 percent were Brahmin/Chhetri. Around 29 percent had good academic performance. Almost all fathers (98.47%) and mothers (99.99%) were literate and nearly 60 percent of fathers and around 50 percent of mothers had completed bachelor level. More than half (51.82%) of respondent's fathers engaged in business, while nearly 50 percent of their mothers were engaged in house-making.

Table 2: Respondent's Information on Bullying

n=137

Information	Frequency(f)	Percentage (%)
Heard about Bullying		
Yes	135	98.54
No	2	1.45
If yes, Kind of Bullying Heard*		
Giving the bad nickname	90	66.67
Threaten to do the things that don't want to do	76	56.29
Private touching	40	29.62
Locked indoors	36	26.67
Sources of Information*		
Social media	84	62.22
School	46	34.07
Family/friends/relatives	34	25.18
Health personnel	5	3.7
Ever been bullied at home?		
Yes	15	10.94
No	120	89.05
If yes From whom you have been bullied*		
Brother	9	60
Sister	4	26.67
Father	2	13.33
Mother	0	0
Ever been Bullied at School		
Yes	101	74.81
No	34	25.18
If yes, from whom you have been bullied*		
Teacher/Staff	22	21.78
Classmates	67	66.33
Seniors	9	8.92
Juniors	3	2.97
Gender among victims of bullying		
Male	61	60.39
Female	40	39.61

* = Multiple responses

(Table 2) shows that almost all (98.54%) of the respondents had heard about bullying and more than 60 percent had heard from social media. The kind of bullying heard by the majority (66.67%) of the students was giving bad nicknames. Almost 11 percent had been bullied at home, among them 60 percent were bullied by their brothers and nearly 75 percent had been bullied at school, among them 66.33 percent were bullied by classmates. Among students male were more bullied than female.

Table 3: Physical Bullying among Respondents

n=101		
Statement	Frequency(f)	Percentage (%)
I have been intentionally hit by my seniors, juniors, classmates, teachers, and other staff.		
Rarely	62	61.38
Occasionally	29	28.71
Frequently	10	9.91
My friends slapped me for no reason as I was a fresher in my class.		
Rarely	74	73.26
Occasionally	14	13.86
Frequently	13	12.88
I have been bitten by my friends when I did not lend them my tiffin.		
Rarely	70	69.31
Occasionally	22	21.78
Frequently	9	8.91
The teacher pulled my hair or gave punishments without my any mistakes.		
Rarely	52	51.49
Occasionally	30	29.70
Frequently	19	18.81
My friends called me by pinching for no reason.		
Rarely	43	42.58
Occasionally	31	30.69
Frequently	27	26.73
My seniors and classmates pushed me intentionally on the school bus, toilet, canteen, stairs, etc.		
Rarely	80	79.20
Occasionally	16	15.85

Frequently	5	4.95
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(Table 3) represents that nearly 10 percent of the respondents were intentionally hit by their seniors, juniors, classmates, teachers, or other staff frequently. Around 13 percent were slapped for no reason. Nearly 22 percent were occasionally bitten by their friends when they didn't lend their tiffin. Around 19 percent were pulled hair or punished by their teacher without any mistakes. Nearly 27 percent were pinched for no reason. Almost 5 percent were pushed intentionally in school buses, toilets, canteen, and stairs.

Table 4: Verbal Bullying among Respondents

n=101

Statement	Frequency(f)	Percentage (%)
I have been threatened by my friends in the name of money, food, assignments, etc.		
Rarely	86	85.14
Occasionally	7	6.94
Frequently	8	7.92
I have been given bad nicknames by my classmates, seniors, juniors, teachers, and staff.		
Rarely	20	19.80
Occasionally	62	61.39
Frequently	19	18.81
I have been rumored by my friends		
Rarely	40	39.60
Occasionally	48	47.53
Frequently	13	12.87

(Table 4) represents that around 8 percent of the respondents had been threatened by their friends in the name of money, food, and assignments. Nearly 19 percent had been given bad nicknames by classmates, seniors, juniors, teachers, or staff frequently. Almost 13 percent were rumored by their friends.

Table 5: Psychological Bullying among Respondents

n=101

Statement	Frequency(f)	Percentage (%)
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My friends or seniors took away my personal belongings or pocket money intentionally.		
Rarely	95	94.05
Occasionally	4	3.97
Frequently	2	1.98
I have been ignored or excluded from the group.		
Rarely	82	81.18
Occasionally	12	11.89
Frequently	7	6.93
I have been compelled to do things that I don't Prefer.		
Rarely	86	85.14
Occasionally	10	9.91
Frequently	5	4.95

(Table 5) depicts that, almost 2 percent of the respondent's friends or seniors had frequently taken away their personal belongings or pocket money intentionally. Nearly 7 percent had been frequently ignored or excluded from the group and almost 5 percent had been frequently compelled to do things that they don't prefer.

Table 6: Sexual Bullying among Respondents

n=101		
Statement	Frequency(f)	Percentage (%)
My friends, seniors, teachers, and other staff touched my private parts without any permission.		
Rarely	99	98.02
Occasionally	2	1.98
Frequently	0	0.00
My friends, seniors, and teachers forced me to watch sexual videos.		
Rarely	98	97.02
Occasionally	2	1.99
Frequently	1	0.99
I have been tortured by the bad gesture body at school		
Rarely	95	94.05
Occasionally	5	4.96
Frequently	1	0.99

(Table 6) illustrates that nearly 2 percent of the respondent's friends, seniors, teachers and other staffs had touched their private parts without their permission and they were forced to watch sexual meaning

videos occasionally. Almost 5 percent had been occasionally tortured by the bad gesture body at school.

Table 7: Different Forms of Bullying among Respondents

n=101		
➤ Items	Frequency(f)	Percentage (%)
Verbal		
Mean± S.D=4±2		
Low (<2)	43	42.57
Average (2-6)	30	29.70
High (>6)	28	27.73
Physical		
Mean± S.D=8±4		
Low (<4)	74	73.26
Average (4-12)	18	17.82
High (>12)	9	8.92
Psychological		
Mean± S.D=4±2		
Low (<2)	70	69.31
Average (2-6)	12	11.88
High (>6)	19	18.81
Sexual		
Mean± S.D=4±2		
Low (<2)	90	89.10
Average (2-6)	8	7.92
High (>6)	3	2.98

(Table 7) represents that among the bullied students, 27.73 percent had experienced high verbal bullying followed by high psychological (18.81%), physical (8.92%) and sexual (2.98%) bullying respectively.

Table 8: Overall Status of Bullying among Respondents

n=101		
Bullying Status	Frequency(f)	Percentage (%)
Low Bullying (<Mean-SD; <11)	49	48.51
Average Bullying (Mean±S.D; 11-25)	40	39.60

High Bullying (>Mean+SD; >25)	12	11.88
Mean ± SD = 18 ± 7		

(Table 8) presents that the mean score of the status of bullying among respondents was 18. Nearly 50 percent of them were victims of low bullying while 11.88 percent experienced high bullying at their school.

Table 9: Association of Bullying Status with Socio-Demographic Variables

n= 101

Variables	Bullying Status			χ^2	df	p-value
	High	Average	Low			
Age in Years						
<15	16(15.84%)	24(23.76%)	29(28.71%)	7.68	2	0.666
>15	6(5.94%)	8(7.92%)	18(17.82%)			
Sex						
Male	18(17.82%)	12(11.88%)	31(30.69%)	6.13	2	0.041*
Female	11(10.89%)	14(13.86%)	15(14.85%)			
Religion						
Hindu	12(11.88%)	24(23.76%)	41(40.59%)	7.03	6	0.333
Non-Hindu	4(3.96%)	7(6.93%)	13(12.83%)			
Ethnicity						
Brahmin/Chhetri	15(14.85%)	22(21.78%)	33(32.67%)	11.69	2	0.421
Janajati/ Dalit	7(6.93%)	12(11.88%)	12(11.88%)			
Class						
Class 9-10	14(13.86%)	28(27.72%)	35(34.65%)	6.46	6	0.370
Class 11- 12	4(3.96%)	7(6.93%)	13(12.87%)			
Academic Performance						
Outstanding, Excellent	9(8.91%)	10(9.90%)	21(20.79%)	13.59	2	0.930
Very Good, Good, Satisfactory	10(9.90%)	37(36.63%)	14(13.86%)			
Father's Occupation						
Service	6(5.94%)	5(4.95%)	8(7.92%)	9.08	4	0.040*
Business	5(4.95%)	8(7.92%)	12(11.88%)			
Foreign Employed	18(17.82%)	14(13.86%)	25(24.75%)			
Mother's Occupation						
House Maker	8(7.92%)	16(15.84%)	13(12.87%)	13.09	4	0.010*
Service	11(10.89%)	5(4.95%)	15(14.85%)			

Business	5(4.95%)	8(7.92%)	20(19.80%)
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**P-value significant at < 0.05*

(Table 9) reveals that there was a statistically significant association of the status of bullying with the sex of the respondents ($p=0.041$), father's occupation ($p=0.040$), and mother's occupation ($p=0.010$).

DISCUSSION

The present study revealed that Almost all (98.54%) of the respondents had heard about bullying which is consistent with the finding of the study conducted in Korea where almost all (96%) had heard about bullying.^[11] In this study more than half (74.81%) of the respondents were bullied at school which is similar to the findings from Iran where the rate of victimization was in between 30 – 60 %^[12] but the different finding was reported by the study conducted in Tehran which found comparatively lower rate of bullying victimization (25%) at school.^[13] this inconsistency may be due to difference in methodology, environmental factors, cultural diversity and the socioeconomic status and education level of the respondents.

Regarding the sources of information on bullying, social media, School, family and friends. The current study revealed that the most common source of information on bullying was social medias (62.2%) followed by school (34.07%) and family/ friends (25.18%). Similar findings were reported by the study conducted in Iran where the common source of information was social media (53.8%).^[13]

With regards to the status of different forms of bullying, the present study demonstrated nearly 43 percent of the respondents had experienced low verbal bullying followed by average (29.70%) and high (27.73%) verbal bullying. This finding is supported by the study conducted in Tamil Naidu, India and Brasil which showed that nearly half (49.7%) of the respondents were victimized by verbal bullying.^[14,15] The current study found that 17.82 percent had experienced average physical bullying and 8.92 percent had experienced high physical bullying which corresponds to the result of a study conducted in Bengaluru, India with average physical bullying of 20.18 percent.^[16] Moreover, with regards to sexual bullying, 7.92 percent and 2.98 percent respectively had experienced high sexual bullying and low sexual bullying. The findings were in line with the findings reported by the study conducted in Italy which showed that less than 10 percent of the respondents were victim of sexual bullying.^[17] The present study revealed that 18.81% and 11.88 % respectively had experienced high and average psychological bullying This finding was different from the findings of the study conducted in Tamil Naidu, India which showed that nearly 50 percent were victimized by psychological bullying.^[14] The finding of this study revealed that nearly 12 percent of the respondents were bullied highly at school which is consistent with the study conducted in China where almost 10 percent were a victim of high bullying at School.^[18] In contrast, 39.60 percent of the students experienced average bullying in this study but the study conducted in Kuwait reported more than half of the respondents had experienced average bullying at school.^[19]

In this study statistically significant association was observed between the status of bullying and sex of the respondents ($p=0.041$) which was consistent with the study conducted in Brazil, Saude and Colombia which reported that the male adolescents were greater involved in aggressive behaviors. [20,21,22] This may be due to the reason that male have higher ability to deal with conflict, aggressive behavior and threats. [15,23,24] In addition to this, the present study depicts that there was a significant association between the father's occupation ($p=0.04$) and mother's occupation ($p=0.01$) which is consistent with the study carried out in Kathmandu, Nepal which showed that the bullying status is associated with father's and mother's occupation. [8]

CONCLUSION

The study concluded that majority of the students were victims of bullying at school. There was a statistically significant association of the status of bullying with the sex of respondents and occupation of their father and mother. Bullying is more prevalent among boys than in girls. This research provides insight into the consequences of bullying and emerging mental health issues among school children. It seems crucial to plan and conduct such programs that can enhance the student's awareness regarding bullying to minimize its consequences among them.

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